

SECURING USER EXPERIENCE: A SURVEY ON INFORMATION SECURITY CONTROLS IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

Information security in education is more important than ever in a digital world. As educational institutions use technology to improve learning, protecting sensitive data is crucial. Over time, information security has become a socio-technical issue, incorporating both technology and human elements. It is also widely believed that insiders with privileged access to the organization's systems and data are the key information security concern. For instance, bring your own device, which offers users access to the internal network and sensitive data, benefits enterprises but also increases security threats. End users are the most vulnerable aspect of information security, but some researchers believe they are the most important asset in protecting enterprises. As "the first line of defense", end users must be vigilant and skilled to secure organizations. Thus, organizations must include human factors in security. Despite various security technology studies, end-user factors have been little studied. Therefore, this research evaluates information security controls used by end-users, notably students in an educational setting. A Likert scale-based questionnaire was given to 378 university students as primary data collection. Validated scales and study objectives-related items based on the Center of Internet Security (CIS) Controls, which comprise basic security procedures for hygiene and cyber attack protection, were included in a structured survey questionnaire. Overall, the mean score indicates modest information security control maturity, with several areas having strong procedures but others needing improvement to enhance security. This study, like others, has limitations; for instance, the university's current network infrastructure and security operations organizational setup were not included because of the risk of external and internal attacks. Disclosing this information could compromise the network infrastructure and other critical servers. Furthermore, the generalizability of this study's findings may be limited to specific organizational contexts, as various qualities, corporate culture, and technology frameworks might have varying impacts on information security controls. Hence, it is imperative for future research to address these constraints by undertaking cross-industry investigations, integrating additional information security measures, employing a longitudinal study framework, and evaluating controls in the face of increasing cybersecurity risks.

Additionally, examining and comparing different organizational environments might provide insights into the aspects that contribute to the efficiency of information security.

Index Terms: Information Security, Information Security Controls, Information Security in Higher Education

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1. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid expansion of mobile devices, applications, and the pervasive utilization of the Internet and social media, it is imperative for enterprises to adapt to the dynamic information technology (IT) landscape in order to maintain relevance and competitiveness. However, the continuous production of new technologies leads to the discovery of newly emerging vulnerabilities, which then transform into emergent threats. With today's highly dynamic IT landscape, maintaining effective information security to secure and preserve essential digital assets has presented numerous issues.

Nowadays, the issue of information security (infosec) has emerged as a significant problem for the majority of organizations. Consequently, organizations have allocated substantial financial resources towards implementing IT solutions as a means of safeguarding themselves against potential security threats. In fact, the application of IT has quickly become the single most essential component of modern security threat solutions. Organizations have started using technical measures, such as firewalls, intrusion protection systems (IPS), and anti-virus software, as a means to safeguard their organizational systems and networks. However, numerous experts and scholars contend that the field of infosec should not solely prioritize technology remedies. Instead, it should also encompass the human dimension, particularly in relation to individuals' behaviors and involvement in security measures [1], [2].

Over time, the field of infosec has evolved into a socio-technical concern because it encompasses not only technological aspects, but also the influence of human elements [3]. In addition, infosec encompasses the examination of users' perceptions regarding the importance of security, their responsibilities, patterns of behavior, and the appropriate amount of security measures required inside an organization.

Moreover, it is widely recognized that the primary concern for the organization's infosec lies with the insiders who have privileged access to its systems and data. Recent surveys have indicated that a significant proportion of information security breaches can be attributed to human factors, including the inappropriate utilization or deliberate exploitation of computer resources, or due to intentional or unintentional, and naive or accidental human behaviors [4][5]. In addition, it has been observed that they are frequently targeted by external attackers due to their limited understanding of potential vulnerabilities to cyber assaults and other critical security concerns prevalent in numerous organizational settings [6] [7]. However, it has been contended by some scholars that while end users are commonly perceived as the most vulnerable aspect of infosec, they are also recognized as the most crucial asset in safeguarding organizations from diverse threats [8]. Consequently, they are often referred to as "the first line of defense". It is also clear that end users' vigilance and skill impact the success of an organization's security measures. As a result, businesses must address the human factor as part of a comprehensive security strategy.

1.1. Information Security in Education

In the study and practice of infosec, professionals and academics rely heavily on technological solutions, including software, physical devices, and operational procedures. as a primary strategy for preventing breaches [9][10]. The adoption of infosec measures plays a crucial role in safeguarding an organization's information assets, reputation, integrity, personnel, and other valuable resources [11]. One of the primary concerns of infosec in education is the protection and preservation of student and staff data.

In an era dominated by digital landscape, the importance of information security in education has never been more critical. As educational institutions increasingly rely on technology to enhance learning experiences, the need to protect sensitive data has become paramount. The security landscape within the education sector include several forms of cyber threats, such as social engineering, phishing attacks that specifically target students and teachers, ransomware incidents that disrupt academic operations, and potential data breaches that compromise important student information.

Educational institutions store vast amounts of confidential information, including student records, academic research, and administrative data. A breach in this information could lead to severe consequences such as identity theft, financial fraud, or even compromise the safety of individuals. In addition, educational databases, often interconnected with various systems, pose a significant challenge, requiring comprehensive security measures to prevent unauthorized access. Furthermore, the rise of remote learning has introduced new vulnerabilities. Virtual classrooms, online assessments, and collaborative platforms have become integral parts of the education system. Yet, they also present potential entry points for cyber threats. Institutions must prioritize securing these virtual spaces, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of educational content. In addition to external threats, internal risks cannot be ignored. Negligence or lack of awareness among students and staff may inadvertently expose the institution to vulnerabilities. Thus, it is crucial that those who have access to sensitive information or regular users align their objectives with those of infosec experts and possess a comprehensive understanding of the essential security measures.

1.2. Bring Your Own Device (BYOD)

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the presence of the bring your own device (BYOD) trend in the IT industry. With the increasing prevalence of personal mobile devices such as mobile phones and tablets being used to access corporate data, a trend known as BYOD, enterprises are recognizing that permitting this form of access can lead to cost reduction and enhanced productivity [12]. It enables employees to utilize their personal computer devices, such as laptops, cellphones, and/or tablets, at work and integrate them into the network of the corporation or organization, instead of relying on devices provided by the firm. Employers considered it as a cost-effective method for reducing expenses in the organization's IT infrastructure and equipment. Similarly, employees find this idea appealing since it offers a higher level of convenience in employing a technology of their preference to perform office tasks. Employees need a work environment that enables them to utilize any device, from any location, and seamlessly integrate personal and work-related tasks at any given moment. This trend is a result of the increasing influence of IT consumerism [13]. In addition, the adoption of BYOD is increasingly becoming the standard rather than the rare occurrence [14].

While BYOD may initially appear as a cost-effective strategy for many enterprises and corporations, it can ultimately prove to be more costly due to the challenges associated with managing multiple platforms.

Furthermore, there are significant security concerns that still need to be resolved. Several prominent firms and organizations opt against altering their security policies and transitioning to BYOD due to their aversion to the heightened vulnerability to cyber threats and data breaches. One significant factor that deters many organizations from adopting BYOD is its relatively recent emergence and the multitude of security risks it presents, particularly in terms of data security. These risks can be found in the devices themselves or even in the applications installed on them. Consequently, firms encounter a multitude of inquiries while developing a BYOD strategy.

Although there are advantages to adopting BYOD in organizations, it has also introduced new security vulnerabilities for organizations [15]. Introducing BYOD policy in the organization poses a risk of security breaches since it grants users' devices access to the internal network and sensitive organizational data [16]. [17] posits that the utilization of personal devices within organizations has been a significant factor in more than 50% of information security breaches, since employees frequently neglect to adhere to information security protocols. According to literature, the most difficult security concerns for BYOD include data leakage, distributed denial of service (DDoS), and malware. Similarly, literature frequently highlights difficulties related to governance, policy, risk management, users' adherence, demeanor, and confidentiality [18]. In the field of information technology, there are frequent discussions regarding network-related problems, policies, risk management, and the adoption of optimal procedures. Aside from safeguarding corporate data, the implementation of BYOD also entails the need to protect private information and manage legal concerns, which, if left unattended, can have detrimental effects on a company [19]. Additional significant factors to consider include device enrollment, assessment of licensing, formulation of security policies, ensuring compliance, providing education, and conducting security training.

In a similar vein, over the past decade, educational institutions have noticed a growing trend among students and teachers to use computers, smartphones, and tablets as tools to enhance their learning experience, even though it is not a formally defined term. The majority of educational institutions have permitted BYOD into their campus, primarily through the use of network access control, without establishing any specific BYOD policy. Exposing institution's networks to student devices poses significant risks, including illegal access, malware and virus attacks, and potential data loss.

1.3. Information Security Controls

In the rapidly evolving landscape of digital technology, where information serves as a cornerstone of modern enterprises, the need for robust infosec controls has never been more critical. Infosec control standards play a pivotal role in guiding organizations towards the implementation of effective measures that safeguard sensitive data and ensure the integrity of digital ecosystems. Some examples of well recognized standards for information security controls include the ISO/IEC 27001, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) SP 800-53, the Center for Internet Security (CIS), and the Control Objectives for Information and Related Technologies (COBIT).

Information security controls are crucial components in safeguarding sensitive data and ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, availability of information [20][21]. These controls are mechanisms, policies, procedures, and technologies designed to mitigate risks and protect information assets from unauthorized access, disclosure, alteration, or destruction [22].

One fundamental category of information security controls is preventive controls [23], [24]. These measures aim to security incidents before they occur. For example, access controls which limit user privileges, ensuring that individuals only have the necessary permissions for their roles. Another is encryption which transforms data into a secure format, rendering it unreadable without the appropriate decryption key.

Detective controls are another vital aspect of infosec controls which focus on identifying and responding to security incidents in a timely manner, such as intrusion detection systems, log monitoring, and security audits [23], [24]. Intrusion detection systems analyze network or system activities for signs of malicious behavior, while log monitoring reviews system logs for unusual activities. In addition, security audits involve systematic evaluation of security policies, processes, and controls to ensure compliance and identify vulnerabilities.

Additionally, corrective controls which come into play after an incident has been detected [23], [24]. Incident response plans, backups and system patches are some examples. Incident response plans outline the steps to be taken when a security incident occurs, helping organizations respond swiftly and effectively. Regular backups ensure that data can be restored in case of data loss or compromise. In addition, system patches involve updating software to address known vulnerabilities and strengthen security.

Lastly, there are also administrative controls that involve policies, procedures and awareness training. Policies define the rules and guidelines for secure behavior, while procedures provide step-by-step instructions for implementing these policies [23], [24]. Awareness training educates end-users about security best practices, fostering a culture security withing an organization. Similarly, BYOD security challenges encompass any security concerns that pose a threat to an organization's assets by exploiting vulnerabilities. To limit the risks to the organization's assets, the establishment of controls is necessary [18].

Therefore, given the prevalence of security threats and risks is growing at an alarming rate, it is essential for a university to undertake an assessment and evaluation of the information security environment that is currently in place. This survey puts a particular emphasis on the information security controls that end-users are using to safeguard their own digital assets.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a cross-sectional research design to investigate the current infosec landscape of the university under studied particularly on the security controls being utilized by the students. By using a cross-sectional technique, data were gathered at a particular point in time, offering a snapshot of the intended population.

2.1. Sources of Data

The target population for this research comprised of undergraduate students enrolled in Bicol University, Legazpi City, Philippines during the academic year 2022-2023. A comprehensive sampling frame was obtained from the university registrar's office, ensuring an accurate representation of the entire population. The sample size was determined using a confidence level of 95%, and a margin of error of ± 5 . This calculation provided a required sample size of 378, ensuring sufficient statistical power. Participants were selected through a random sampling technique. Given the diverse nature of the university population, the sampling approach incorporated stratification. The population was stratified based on academic colleges. Proportional random sampling was then applied within each stratum, guaranteeing that each sub-group was adequately represented in the final sample.

2.2. Data Collection

The primary data collection method is a Likert scale-based questionnaire administered to students across various colleges in the university. A structured survey questionnaire was developed incorporating validated scales and items relevant to the research objectives. The scale consists of statements related to different information security controls, including access management, encryption protocols, awareness training, and incident response. The primary material was a meticulously designed survey questionnaire based on the Center of Internet Security (CIS) Controls which include foundational security measures that can be used to achieve essential hygiene and protect against a cyber attack. Participants were asked to rate their level of frequency with each statement on a five-point Likert scale (1 = never, 2 = rarely, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often, 5 = always). The survey instrument underwent a pilot test with a small group of participants. Feedback from the pilot study was used to refine and finalize the questionnaire.

In addition, participants were provided with clear instructions regarding the purpose of the study, the Likert scale response format, and assurances of confidentiality. The data collection period spans one semester, allowing for a sufficient number of responses. Selected participants were approached through e-mail and on-campus distribution, and invited to participate in the survey using Google Form. Similarly, informed consent was obtained from each participant.

2.3. Data Analysis and Synthesis

Quantitative data collected through the Likert scale responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as means for each scale item.

2.4. Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained during the data collection process. In addition, all data collected were treated with utmost confidentiality since the subject matter to be investigated pertains to security. The results and findings of this research project was anonymized, and did not provide any associations of the respondents such as their names and email addresses.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The assessment of information security controls in the university reveals a diverse environment in terms of the effectiveness of implemented measures. The mean ratings achieved for each control category provide significant insights into the perceived level of maturity of the information security posture within the studied environment. Table 1 presents the mean scores for each information security control.

3.1. Inventory and Control of Software Assets

The Inventory and Control of Software Assets security control is a crucial element in an organization's cybersecurity framework to ensure that organizations maintain an accurate and up-to-date record of all software assets that have been implemented. Through the establishment of a comprehensive inventory, businesses may effectively oversee and regulate software, thereby mitigating security risks linked to mismanaged or unauthorized programs. This control involves continuously monitoring software installations, updates, and deletions. It enables organizations to enforce licensing agreements, discover and resolve vulnerabilities, and promptly address any instances of illegal or dangerous programs. The average score of 3.02/5.0 suggests a moderate degree of effectiveness. The focus on creating an inventory is in accordance with recognizing the significance of software expertise. Nevertheless, it is advisable to pursue further instruction in order to augment user consciousness, so guaranteeing that students actively participate in upholding precise software inventories.

3.2. Data Protection

Data Protection security control is an essential element of a strong cybersecurity strategy, specifically designed to protect sensitive and confidential information within an organization. This control implements a comprehensive strategy to prevent, identify, and address unauthorized entry, disclosure, modification, and destruction of sensitive information. Implementation often encompasses the encryption of data during transmission and storage, strong access controls, routine data backups, and the adoption of explicit policies controlling data management. A mean score of 3.11 out of 5.0 indicates a moderate level of efficacy. The focus on encryption techniques and the thorough approach to safeguarding data at every stage is encouraging. Nevertheless, continuous security awareness training is essential to ensure that students comprehend their responsibility in upholding data protection.

Table 1. Information Security Controls and its Mean Scores

Information Security Control	Mean
Inventory and Control of Software Assets Actively manage (make an inventory, track and correct) installed software in your computer device	3.02
Data Protection Use data protection controls such as encryption tools to identify, classify, securely handle, retain, and dispose of data	3.11
Secure Configuration of Enterprise Assets and Software Establish and maintain security configuration in your computer such as automatic session locking (i.e. automatically locks after a period of inactivity), automatic device lockout, disable default accounts and unnecessary services	3.59
Account Management Observe a good practice in managing your accounts such as maintaining an inventory of accounts, using unique passwords and disabling dormant accounts	4.09
Access Control Management Observe a good practice in granting, managing and revoking rights and privileges for other user accounts for digital resources (i.e. file sharing, printer sharing)	3.65
Continuous Vulnerability Management Assess and track vulnerabilities in your computer in order to remediate, and minimize, the window of opportunity for attackers	3.30
Audit Log Management Enable the audit logging feature available in your operating system (e.g. Windows) to collect audit log events that could help you detect, understand, or recover from an attack	2.93
Email and Web Browser Protections Enable your security tools (e.g. anti-spam software; anti-adware; pop-up blockers) in your browser to actively improve the protections and detections of threats from email and web vectors, as these are opportunities for attackers to manipulate human behavior through direct engagement	3.78
Malware Defenses Actively run anti-malware software (e.g. anti-virus) in your computer to prevent or control the installation, spread, and execution of malicious applications, code, or scripts	3.74
Data Recovery Perform data recovery (backup) practices sufficient to restore pre-incident and trusted state	3.64
Networking Monitoring and Defense Install user-based/host-based tools (e.g. host-based intrusion protection system – IPS; host-based intrusion detection system – IDS) to establish and maintain network monitoring and defense against security threats	2.60
Security Awareness and Skills Training Recognize social engineering attacks, and able to practice proper data handling techniques	2.90
Incident Response Management Properly respond (e.g. handle, manage and report) to security incidents	3.38
Overall Mean	3.36

3.3. Secure Configuration of Enterprise Assets and Software

Ensuring the deployment of Secure Configuration for Enterprise Assets and Software security control is vital for enhancing an organization’s cyber defenses. This method primarily focuses on optimizing the configuration settings of both hardware and software assets in order to boost security. This control focuses on prioritizing the establishment and maintenance of secure configurations to reduce vulnerabilities and effectively mitigate future cyber threats.

The process involves creating and implementing a consistent configuration baseline for all organizational assets, including network devices and workstations. Continuous monitoring, periodic security assessments, and automated technologies are frequently employed to ensure that settings remain secure and compliant with industry standards. An average score of 3.59/5.0 indicates a comparatively high degree of efficacy in building and upholding security setups. Positive indicators encompass the implementation of automatic session locking and device lockout, which prioritize physical security. The primary objective of user training should be to comprehend the underlying reasoning behind security controls, hence facilitating long-term adherence to compliance requirements.

3.4. Account Management

The Account Management security control is an essential element of cybersecurity, focusing on the effective administration and oversight of user accounts to ensure that user accounts are created, altered, and deactivated in compliance with established policies and procedures. Organizations can implement the principle of least privilege by formulating robust account management procedures, which entail granting personnel access only to the necessary resources for their specified duties. Furthermore, enterprises often employ identity and access management (IAM) solutions to automate and streamline account management activities.

The Account Management security control is essential for preventing unauthorized access, mitigating internal threats, and maintaining an accurate record of user privileges, so significantly enhancing overall cybersecurity resilience. The average score of 4.09 out of 5.0 indicates a significant degree of efficacy. Engaging in positive behaviors such as regularly updating an account inventory, employing distinct passwords, and deactivating inactive accounts demonstrate a proactive stance towards ensuring account security. It is advisable to provide students with regular training on secure password habits in order to actively empower them.

3.5. Access Control Management

The Access Control Management security control is an essential component in safeguarding sensitive information and critical systems inside an organization's cybersecurity framework. This security control is intended to regulate and oversee the access to resources, ensuring that only authorized users have the ability to interact with certain data, applications, or systems. Access Control Management encompasses the implementation of robust authentication and authorization systems, which incorporate principles like least privilege to assign individuals with the minimum level of access required for their respective responsibilities. Implementing access controls enables organizations to prevent unauthorized access attempts, mitigate data breaches, and comply with regulatory obligations.

The implementation of the Access Control Management security control is essential for developing a strong defense against both internal and external threats, hence enhancing overall resilience in cybersecurity. The average score of 3.65/5.0 indicates a moderate to high degree of efficacy. Implementing a comprehensive strategy for access control, which encompasses a wide range of digital resources, is advantageous. It is advisable to undergo training on access controls and their significance in order to maintain long-term efficacy.

3.6. Continuous Vulnerability Management

Continuous Vulnerability Management is an active and adaptable security measure that is essential for detecting and resolving potential vulnerabilities in an organization's systems. This security control prioritizes the continuous and methodical evaluation of assets to identify security weaknesses.

By conducting routine scans, tests, and monitoring, companies can identify weaknesses in software, networks, and configurations. Continuous Vulnerability Management encompasses the process of not just detecting vulnerabilities, but also assessing their significance by considering their potential impact and the likelihood of being exploited. Organizations can mitigate the danger of exploitation, lower the likelihood of attacks, and strengthen their overall cybersecurity resilience by rapidly fixing vulnerabilities.

Continuous Vulnerability Management security control is a crucial component of a proactive cybersecurity strategy, advocating for a diligent and flexible approach to safeguarding against evolving threats. The average score of 3.30 out of 5.0 indicates a moderate degree of effectiveness. It is advisable to undergo vulnerability management training in order to improve one's abilities in evaluating and resolving problems. Furthermore, proactive vulnerability management places significant emphasis on prioritizing, continuous monitoring, and the integration of incident response.

3.7. Audit Log Management

Audit Log Management is an essential security measure that focuses on the systematic collection, storage, analysis, and retention of audit logs. Implementing this security control is essential for ensuring accountability, monitoring activities, and detecting any security breaches.

Audit Log Management involves the detailed logging of system events and user activity, resulting in a comprehensive trail that can be carefully examined and assessed for security and compliance purposes. Frequent analysis of audit logs enables firms to identify atypical or dubious activities, unauthorized login attempts, or potential breaches in security.

In addition, by effectively managing audit logs, businesses can enhance their capacity to address issues, conduct thorough investigations, and demonstrate their adherence to security policies and regulatory requirements. The average score of 2.93/5.0 indicates a reasonable degree of efficacy in facilitating audit tracking capabilities. To enhance cybersecurity measures, the university should prioritize the configuration of comprehensive logging, conducting regular reviews, and integrating advanced analysis tools. These actions will enable a more proactive and effective utilization of audit logs for cybersecurity reasons, going beyond the baseline implementation.

3.8. Email and Web Browser Protections

Email and Web Browser Protections are a vital security measure that enhances an organization's ability to defend against cyber threats that often exploit vulnerabilities in email and web browsers. This security measure is specifically tailored to mitigate the dangers associated with phishing efforts, malicious websites, and the inadvertent downloading of harmful content. By integrating robust safeguards into email systems and online browsers, organizations may significantly reduce the likelihood of individuals becoming targets of socially engineered attacks. The key elements of this security strategy entail the utilization of email filtering algorithms to identify and segregate malicious attachments or links. Furthermore, online browser precautions include the incorporation of secure browsing features, URL filtering, and content inspection to discourage users from accessing potentially dangerous websites.

Email and Web Browser Protections are essential elements of a multi-tiered defensive system, acting as the first line of defense against threats that often exploit human vulnerabilities. The average score of 3.78 out of 5.0 suggests a significantly high degree of efficacy.

Enabling security features such as anti-spam software, anti-adware, and pop-up blockers is widely acknowledged as essential. It is advisable to provide regular training to users to increase their understanding of identifying and avoiding email and web-based dangers. This will help maintain a proactive and efficient approach to cybersecurity.

3.9. Malware Defenses

Malware Defenses are essential security measures designed to prevent, detect, and respond to harmful software threats. Efficient strategies for countering malware encompass a comprehensive approach that entails the use of anti-virus software, intrusion prevention systems, and endpoint protection solutions. Furthermore, taking proactive steps, such as consistently updating signature databases and utilizing heuristic analysis, allows enterprises to detect and prevent both established and developing malware threats. Implementing continuous monitoring and automatic responses to identified malware cases enhances the speed and efficiency of our security strategy.

Malware defenses are essential for preserving the integrity of an organization's digital environment, safeguarding against data breaches, and assuring uninterrupted business operations in the presence of more complex and advanced malware attacks. The average score of 3.74 out of 5.0 suggests a considerably high level of efficacy. Utilizing anti-malware software actively demonstrates a proactive approach to preventing and managing malware risks. Consistently updating with the most recent virus definitions is essential for maintaining and improving this effectiveness. A strong defense against malware is achieved through a consistent emphasis on user education, implementation of sophisticated threat detection technologies, and seamless interaction with wider security activities.

3.10. Data Recovery

Data Recovery is an essential security measure that aims to guarantee the accessibility and reliability of crucial information in the event of unforeseen catastrophes or disasters. This security control entails implementing resilient techniques and protocols to retrieve data and reinstate regular operations following occurrences such as system malfunctions, cyber intrusions, or natural calamities. Efficient solutions for Data Recovery involve the implementation of frequent data backups, storing data in other locations, and creating comprehensive recovery plans. Organizations can mitigate disruptions, expedite the recovery of essential systems, and maintain business continuity in the face of unexpected obstacles by implementing clearly defined recovery procedures and frequently testing backups. The average score of 3.64/5.0 suggests a significantly high degree of efficacy. Engaging in proactive data recovery procedures demonstrates a firm dedication to protecting data and restoring systems to a reliable state.

3.11. Network Monitoring and Defense

Network Monitoring and Defense is a fundamental security measure that involves actively monitoring and safeguarding network infrastructure from cyber attacks. Network Monitoring entails the immediate examination of network traffic, data, and events to detect irregularities or possible security breaches.

Network Monitoring and Defense security control is essential in the ever-changing field of cybersecurity, where protecting sensitive information and key systems is of utmost importance. The average score of 2.60 indicates a moderate degree of effectiveness. There is a recognition of the significance of safeguarding individual users and their devices. Nevertheless, there are indications of obstacles such as resource limitations, technical intricacies, and deficiencies in security knowledge and training.

The result highlights the necessity for the university to enhance their security measures at the user level. Suggested measures including allocating resources towards acquiring sophisticated tools, strengthening security awareness initiatives, and delivering comprehensive training to users to improve their ability to identify and report security risks.

3.12. Security Awareness and Skills Training

Enhancing Security Awareness and Skills Training is a crucial security measure that aims to equip individuals in an organization to actively defend against cyber attacks. This security measure acknowledges the significant influence of human elements in upholding a robust cybersecurity stance. It entails instructing end-users on potential hazards, optimal security methods, and the significance of following organizational security measures. Comprehensive training programs encompass various subjects, such as phishing awareness, password hygiene, social engineering, and the secure utilization of technologies. The average score of 2.90 suggests a moderate degree of effectiveness. The respondents exhibit a fundamental comprehension, however there are areas that might be enhanced. The university can get advantages from specialized training programs that specifically aim to improve awareness of social engineering strategies. It is essential to strengthen the implementation of recommended methods for securely managing data in order to enhance the overall strength of cybersecurity measures. The success of security awareness programs is contingent upon the presence of leadership support, which is deemed crucial.

3.13. Incident Response Management

Incident Response Management is an essential security measure that aims to efficiently identify, address, and restore normalcy once cybersecurity incidents occur within an organization. This security control is specifically designed to reduce the consequences of security breaches, address continuing threats, and expedite the restoration of regular operations. Preserving evidence is crucial for conducting further investigation and strengthening the overall cybersecurity resilience of the company. Moreover, it is in line with a proactive approach to reduce the amount of time when a system is not operational, safeguard confidential information, and uphold the confidence of those involved in the midst of developing cyber risks. The average score of 3.38 suggests a significant level of effectiveness in addressing security incidents. Respondents exhibit a high level of confidence in their capacity to handle, oversee, and document incidents, demonstrating a robust incident response capability.

The overall mean score of 3.36 suggests a modest level of maturity in the evaluated information security controls. While several areas exhibit robust practices, others necessitate attention and enhancement to bolster the overall security stance. To summarize, the evaluation offers significant insights that may be used to prioritize and implement specific enhancements in information security measures. Adopting a comprehensive approach that focuses on the identified gaps and leverages existing strengths will enhance the security environment, making it more robust and resilient. Periodic evaluations and modifications to security measures are crucial in order to effectively respond to changing threats and difficulties.

4. CONCLUSION

This research study concludes with significant findings regarding the current state of information security controls within the examined setting. Several noteworthy findings emerged from the assessment. Upon completing this study, the researcher reached the determination that the current information security protocols exhibit varying levels of effectiveness. While some solutions are effective, others may require enhancement to effectively address the growing cyber threats.

The findings indicate that the level of user awareness and training plays a crucial role in influencing the effectiveness of information security controls. The university should prioritize equipping users with the required knowledge to effectively navigate and address security issues by implementing training programs. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of consistently enhancing technological systems to maintain a robust information security environment. Based on the findings, this research offers several recommendations for enhancing the existing measures aimed at ensuring information security. Firstly, the university should implement comprehensive training programs aimed at augmenting user knowledge and instructing end-users on the latest security threats and optimal methodologies. Also, the institution should employ advanced security technologies, such as encryption tools and anti-virus software, and allocate resources specifically for their deployment. Furthermore, it is imperative to ensure that the security measures align with the regulatory mandates and industry benchmarks to uphold its reputation and safeguard the data. Ultimately, it is advised that the university conduct regular security audits to identify any vulnerabilities and deficiencies in the current security control measures. By implementing this proactive approach, the university can address security weaknesses before they can be exploited.

4.1. Limitation of the Research

This research primarily focused on end-users, specifically examining the information security controls being utilized. Similar to other research, this study has some limitations. As a result, the current organizational set-up of network and security operations in the university was not included. This information cannot be shared with the general public due to the risk of potential external and internal attacks. Disclosing this information could compromise the security of the university's network infrastructure, and other critical servers.

Moreover, although this study offers useful insights into the information security measures in the examined setting, it is crucial to recognize specific constraints that could affect the applicability and extent of the results. The findings of this study are context-specific and may not have universal applicability to other organizational environments. The distinct attributes, corporate culture, and technological framework of the examined context may impact the efficacy of information security measures in a manner distinct from other contexts. The realm of cybersecurity is characterized by its constant evolution, as new threats and technology emerge. The evaluated information security controls in this study accurately depict the current status of cybersecurity inside the analyzed environment at a particular moment in time. The findings may become less relevant over time due to swift technological advancements, evolving threat landscapes, or changes in organizational structures. In addition, the data gathered for this study are based on self-reported answers provided by students within the university. Although attempts were taken to guarantee truthful and precise answers, there is a potential for response bias or the impact of social desirability. Participants might have submitted answers that were biased towards their own preferences rather than accurately reflecting their true behaviors or beliefs. Furthermore, the study primarily examined particular information security controls, which, although essential, only encompass a portion of the wider range of cybersecurity measures. Focusing solely on these measures may fail to consider other significant elements that impact the overall security stance of the university.

Future Research Direction

It is therefore recommended that future research endeavors should focus on overcoming these limitations by conducting cross-industry studies, incorporating a wider array of information security controls, utilizing a longitudinal research design, and investigating the efficacy of controls against emerging cybersecurity threats. Furthermore, doing a comparative analysis across various organizational contexts could offer a more thorough comprehension of the elements that impact the efficiency of information security.

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